

Amphiphilic Chitosan/Poly(L-Lactide) Composite Films: Miscibility and Application for Tissue Engineering Scaffold

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SUMMARY

Amphiphilic *N,N*-dilauryl chitosan/PLLA (NCS/PLLA) composite films with three different weight ratios were prepared by solution approach using CHCl₃ as co-solvent. The miscibility of NCS/LLA composite systems is studied by FTIR, DSC, XRD and SEM techniques. It mainly arises from hydrogen-bonding interactions between the hydroxyl groups of NCS and the carbonyl groups of PLLA. The cell adhesion, cell viability and SEM experimental results indicate that NCS is benefit to improve the cell affinity of PLLA.

Keywords: *N,N*-dilauryl chitosan, poly(L-lactide), composite film, hydrogen-bonding, miscibility.

MAIN CONTENT

Both chitosan and PLLA are good biomaterials. However, the shortcomings are inadequate mechanical properties for chitosan and a little bioactivity for PLLA, respectively. Many previous publications have reported the composites of chitosan and PLLA in order to circumvent the problem. Previous researches have been affirmed that feeble inter-associated hydrogen-bonding interactions existed between chitosan and PLLA. However, strong self-associated hydrogen-bonding interactions within chitosan, no cosolvents shared by chitosan and PLLA, which caused a phase separation exists in chitosan/PLLA composite systems. In this paper, we synthesized a new modified chitosan derivative, *N,N*-dilauryl chitosan (NCS), which bioactive groups —OH and a few —NH₂ are still retained in the main chain of chitosan. Due to the side chain of dilauryl can impair the self-interaction hydrogen-bonding interactions, NCS as an amphiphilic macromolecule, in our tests, can easily dissolve in several organic or aqueous solvents such as CHCl₃, THF, DMSO and glacial HAc. Therefore, it is easy to blend NCS with PLLA by solution approach using their cosolvent. Meanwhile, an abundant of hydroxide groups in NCS will interact with carbonyl groups in PLLA, this interaction is so-called hydrogen-bonding interaction, which is a potential driving force to make the composites miscible. These miscible composite systems containing chitosan are expected to be new materials in the field of biomass utilization, which possess both the biospecific properties of chitosan and the mechanical properties of PLLA. The experimental results show this composite has obviously higher cell affinity than PLLA. The research offers a new concept that the mechanism of miscibility in NCS/PLLA composite films probably is at “nanometer level”, and not at “molecular level”.

Figure 1. The model of hydrogen-bonding interaction in NCS/PLLA composite.

Figure 2. NIH 3T3 growth on the surface of PLLA (left) and NCS/PLLA (right) for 2 days (SEM \times 2000).

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